

THE IMPACT OF SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS IN IMPULSE PURCHASING BEHAVIOUR OF CLOTHES IN BANGLADESH

Fairuz Chowdhury *

Abstract

The study aims to understand the impact of demographic factors- age, gender, household income, and cultural dimensions- individualism/collectivism and power-distance beliefs on impulse purchase tendency among Bangladeshi consumers. Although the author planned and started with a mall-intercept survey method, however, due to the situation arising from the COVID-19 pandemic, he had to shift to using an online questionnaire survey. To analyze the results and test the hypotheses, the author undertook factor analysis and multi-linear regression. The study revealed that only household income shows a positive association with impulse purchase behavior. Surprisingly, there was no association between any of the cultural dimensions to impulse purchasing tendency. At the same time, an interesting observation was that Generation Z consumers exhibit more impulsive purchasing tendencies than their Generation Y counterparts. It is worth mentioning, the use of convenience sampling meant an overrepresentation of two generations (Gen Z and Gen Y). While this led to a new revelation about the purchasing tendencies of consumers of these generations, future research with a larger sample can lead to enhancing the generalization of the findings. The study provides a holistic model incorporating cultural dimensions and demographic factors to expand the understanding of these factors' influence on consumer impulse purchasing tendency for an emerging nation.

Keywords : *Culture, Demographics, Impulse Purchasing, Individualism/Collectivism, Power-Distance Belief.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Impulse purchasing is a crucial area of research in consumer behavior. According to Beatty and Ferrell (1998), impulse purchase is an unanticipated and instant purchase of something without any pre-shopping intent. The interest in this area arises due to the profitability of impulse purchasing. Since the 1950s, many studies have focused on impulse buying behavior, with research concentrating on the USA market. However, with the expansion of global corporates and new emerging markets coming to the fore with the growth in retail space, more and more studies are now focusing on factors influencing impulse purchasing tendency and behaviors of consumers in developing economies (e.g., Nguyen et al., 2003; Bashar et al., 2013).

According to the Economist, Bangladesh is ranked the 9th most robust economy amongst the 66 emerging economies amid the COVID-19 effects (Dhaka Tribune, 2020), enjoying a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth of over 6% over the last

* Assistant Professor, Institute of Business Administration (IBA), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

decade. A study by Munir et al., (2015) claims that the middle-affluent class (MAC) population, those households with more than \$400 income, is growing at a fast pace, an average of 10.5 percent annually, and is expected to reach a population of 34 million by 2025 from 12 million in 2015. The MAC population is a critical metric for businesses and marketers, as these are consumers with purchasing power buying a wide variety of consumer goods. Another vital aspect is consumer optimism, as this translates into a strong desire to buy. Consumers in Bangladesh have a stronger affinity towards a willingness to buy. Munir et al. (2015, p. 8) highlight this case in their study, which claims that sixty-nine percent of respondents in their survey concurred with the statement, "It seems like every year, there are more things I want to buy." This belief is substantially more innate and intense in Bangladesh than in other Southeast Asian nations (Munir et al., 2015). With the increase in the MAC population, combined with the consumer propensity to engage in shopping, this market will keep on inciting marketers' interest.

Although impulse purchasing is often taken to be generic, local conditions, demographics (Khan et al., 2016), and social and cultural factors influence how consumers act on impulse (Nguyen, 2003). Over the years, research has focused on the individualism/collectivism dimension for understanding the cultural orientation and its relation to impulse purchasing (Nguyen, 2003; Kacen & Lee, 2008). However, power-distance belief (PDB) was the initial cultural dimension identified by Hofstede (1984) (Oyserman, 2006). Therefore, it is essential to incorporate the power distance dimension as a cultural construct. Thus, this study aims to expand the understanding of impulse purchasing tendency in a developing country by analyzing the demographic factors and two of the most significant dimensions (individualism/collectivism and power-distance belief) of culture.

The rest of the article is structured with the literature review on the demographic factors and cultural dimensions of interest, followed by a section on the choice of methodology with reasoning. Following these, there are the analysis and results section and a discussion section.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Impulse purchases are relevant for businesses, as this accounts for a significant percentage of sales across multiple product brackets (Rook & Fischer, 1995; Hausman, 2000). According to Karmali (2007), the then CEO of Coca Cola claimed that impulse purchases account for over 70 percent of Coke's sales. Thus, impulse buying is a pervasive facet of consumer behavior.

A review of the existing literature reveals that before the 1980s, researchers defined impulse purchases with a focus on product characteristics rather than consumer characteristics. Since the 1980s, research focus has shifted to consumer traits and behavioral dimensions related to impulse purchases. According to Rook (1987, p. 191), impulse purchase occurs when a consumer experiences a sudden, often powerful, and persistent urge to buy something immediately. Beatty and Ferrell (1998, p. 170) modified this definition by stating impulse purchase as a sudden

and immediate purchase with no pre-shopping intentions either to buy the specific product category or to fulfill a particular buying task.

A study of previous literature links impulse purchases to demographics (Nguyen et al., 2003; Yang et al., 2011) and cultural orientation (Triandis et al., 1988; Nguyen et al., 2003; Zhang et al., 2010). A significant number of studies such as Kollat and Willett (1967), Cobb and Hoyer (1986), Nguyen et al. (2003), Gasiorowska (2011), and Tifferet and Herstein (2012) explained the relationship of gender to impulse purchases. Previous researchers such as Rawlings, Boldero, and Wiseman (1995), Nguyen et al. (2003), and Hulten and Vanyushyn (2014) have studied the impact of age on impulse purchases. In a similar vein, studies by researchers such as Abratt and Goodey (1990) and Nguyen et al. (2003) are available on the effect of income on an impulse purchase. These are critical demographic factors that relate to the study of an impulse purchase.

Previous literature also explains that the cultural dimension impacts impulse purchase behavior. According to Hofstede and Hofstede (2001, p.9), culture is a collective programming of the mind that distinguishes the members of one group of people from another. Of the dimensions proposed by Hofstede and Hofstede (1991), researchers have generally focused on individualism and collectivism dimension and its influence on understanding consumer behavior (Kacen & Lee, 2002; Nguyen et al., 2003). Oyserman's (2006) emphasis that Hofstede recognized the power-distance dimension as the first cultural factor meant research has since focused on the impact of this dimension on impulse purchasing (e.g., Zhang et al., 2010). Thus, the author proposes a holistic model (Figure-1) that incorporates these dimensions of demographic factors, along with these two cultural dimensions.

Figure 1: Overview of Research Model

2.1 Hypotheses

2.1.1 Demographics

2.1.1.1 Gender

Kollat and Willett (1967) state that women are likely to make impulse purchases, but Cobb and Hoyer (1986) claim that men purchase more impulsively. In line with Kollat and Willett (1967), Tifferet and Herstein (2012) claim women are likelier to

make a higher number of impulse purchases than men do due to sensitivity to aesthetic cues that comes about from touching an object. The tenet is in line with Peck and Childers's (2006) belief that the need for touch (NFT) increases the likelihood of inciting an impulse purchase. Furthermore, Coley and Burgess (2003) imply that women are likely to engage in impulse buying of products provoking emotion and stylistic appeal. Regarding the product category -clothing, the author asserts that females are more likely to make more frequent impulse purchases than men.

H₁: Female Bangladeshi consumers are likely to engage in more impulse purchases than men.

2.1.1.2 Age

Previous studies suggest that younger consumers purchase more impulsively (e.g., Rawlings, Boldero, & Wiseman, 1995). In line with this, Nguyen et al. (2003) claim that younger Vietnamese are more likely to engage in impulse purchases. Similarly, Cakanlar and Nguyen's (2019) study reveals a negative relationship between age and impulse purchase, reinforcing that younger people are likely to exhibit impulse purchasing behavior. Thus, the author believes that younger consumers are more likely to make more frequent impulse purchases.

H₂: Younger Bangladeshi consumers are likely to engage in more impulse purchases.

2.1.1.3 Income

Abratt and Goodey (1990) claim that compared to other countries, in the United States, higher income is a significant factor influencing impulse purchase. Similarly, Bashar et al. (2013) argue that disposable income is a significant impulse purchase indicator, but Amos et al. (2014) contradicts this by asserting that income has minimal influence. However, the author expects consumers with higher income levels to be less restrictive and more prone to act on impulse.

H₃: Income positively influences impulse purchase behavior among Bangladeshi consumers.

2.1.2 Cultural Orientation

2.1.2.1 Individualism/Collectivism

While individuals in collectivist society are part of groups that pay attention to these individuals in part for their loyalty, individuals in individualistic society look out for themselves and, at most, their immediate family (Hofstede-Insights, n.d.). According to Triandis et al. (1988), the individualism/collectivism dimension is a crucial cultural construct related to impulse purchasing behavior. The study by Kacen and Lee (2002) is in line with that of Triandis et al.'s (1988), reinforcing individualism/collectivism construct as a vital factor influencing impulse purchasing behavior. In essence, the study claims that individuals in collectivistic cultures are likely to be less inclined to impulse purchases. However, other studies by Kongarakadecha and

Khemarangsang (2012) and Abraham and Dameyasani (2013) reveal that collectivism has a positive relationship with impulse buying behavior. Although there seems to be a divide in the literature on the impact of individualism/ collectivism construct, Bangladesh is a highly collectivistic society scoring similar to Thailand in the individualism dimension (20) (Hofstede-Insights, n.d.), therefore, based on the study by Kongakardecha and Khemarangsang (2012), the author expects collectivism to have a positive relationship with impulse buying behavior.

H₄ : There is a positive association between collectivism construct and impulse purchase behavior among Bangladeshi consumers.

2.1.2.2 Power-Distance

Hofstede (2001, p. 83) explains power distance behavior as the degree to which individuals accept and expect that power is distributed unequally. Previous studies reveal that the power-distance construct impacts impulsive buying behavior. A focus on the present consumption exemplifies Western cultures and is defined by having low scores in the power-distance construct (Chen et al., 2005). Similarly, according to Zhang et al. (2010), individuals in this culture exhibit less self-control, while individuals in high power-distance culture exhibit more definite self-control. Thus, individuals in low power distance are likely to engage in impulse purchases, and power distance impacts impulse purchasing behavior. Bangladesh has a high score (80) in the power-distance dimension, where people acknowledge a pecking order where everyone would fall in (Hofstede-Insights, n.d.). Therefore, as Bangladeshis accept a high power-distance culture, there should be a negative association with impulse purchasing behavior.

H₅ : There is a negative association between power-distance construct and impulse purchase behavior among Bangladeshi consumers.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Collection

For data collection, the author planned to use a single-stage mall-intercept survey method as done in previous studies (Beatty & Ferrell, 1998; Mattila & Wirtz, 2008). The author and volunteers, undergraduate students of the Institute of Business Administration (IBA), University of Dhaka, started the survey across several apparel outlets in Banani, Dhaka, the representative hub for MAC customers of the metropolitan. The author reached out to and visited multiple (18) outlets in the Banani area to ask for permission from the relevant stakeholder to conduct the surveys. However, managers of ten of these outlets agreed to allow the surveys to be carried out outside the respective store. Nonetheless, the author believed that over a month, he would be able to access a representative sample of shoppers. However, since the data collection was taking place towards the end of March 2020, the impact of COVID-19 limited the ability to conduct field surveys. Thus, the author decided to revert to undertaking an online survey, thereby using convenience sampling, a non-

probabilistic sampling technique. The author used his network of friends, family, and colleagues to reach out to people to fill the questionnaire created in google form, a method used in previous studies (Cakanlar & Nguyen, 2019), using social media platforms and emails. The survey, i.e., the google form, was available for 15 days from April 15, 2020 to April 30, 2020.

3.2 Measurements and Methods

The questionnaire had nineteen items, seven questions related to the dependent variable, impulse purchasing behavior, three about the respondents' demographic characteristics, five items about the individualism/collectivism construct, and four questions related to power-distance culture.

For analyzing and measuring the impulse purchasing behavior, the scale was based on the studies by Rook and Fisher (1995) and Hausman (2000) and used a five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree). To measure the individualism/collectivism construct on a five-point Likert scale, the author developed the questions based on Lee and Brislin (1998), Nguyen et al. (2003), and Cakanlar and Nguyen (2019). Similarly, to measure the power-distance cultural dimension on a similar five-point Likert scale, the author based the questions on those used by Hofstede's (2001) and Cakanlar and Nguyen (2019). Regarding the demographic variables, while age had an open-ended option, gender is a binary variable with coded with 0 as males and 1 as females, and monthly income was structured in five tiers.

3.3 Data Analysis Tools

For multi-item scales, the author conducted a factor analysis with Varimax rotation. Although for different sample sizes, different factor loadings will be statistically significant; however, here, the acceptable factor loading is at least 0.60 for considering reliable items (Hair et al., 2014). Items loading significantly in more than one factor were removed from the analysis. To test the hypotheses, the author conducted regression analyses. Data were analyzed using MS Excel and SPSS-16 software platforms at a 95% confidence level.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Sample Profile

The sample size was 266, of which 68% were male, and 32% were female, with an average age of 24.11 years. Interestingly, around 59% of the participants belonged to Generation Z (Gen Z)¹ and 39% in Generation Y (Gen Y)², arising due to the prevalent use of social media and emails by these generations. The income profiles of the participants were pretty well spread across the different income brackets (Table-1). It is worth mentioning our sample size of 266 meets the minimum sample requirement for conducting factor analysis. (Kenhove, Janssens, & Wijen, 2008).

¹ Generation Z belongs to those individuals born between 1995 to 2012 (WJSchroer, n.d.)

² Generation Y belongs to those individuals born between 1977 to 1994 (WJSchroer, n.d.)

Table 1 : Monthly Income Distribution

Income Tiers	Distribution
<Tk. 100000	28%
Tk. 100000- Tk. 200000	23%
Tk. 200000- Tk.300000	17%
Tk. 300000- Tk. 400000	25%
> Tk. 400000	7%

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

Prior to hypothesis testing, exploratory factor analysis was conducted, which revealed two factors of cultural dimensions, and the dependent variable, impulse purchasing tendency. Reliability was analyzed and evaluated through Cronbach's Alpha, α (Details in Table-2).

Table 2 : Results of Factor Analyses

	Impulse Purchasing Tendency $\alpha=0.919$	Power-Distance Cultural Construct $\alpha=0.726$	Individualism/Collectivism construct $\alpha=0.675$
I often buy clothes without thinking-	.896		
Sometimes I'm a bit reckless while shopping for clothes-	.894		
I often buy clothes spontaneously-	.863		
"Buy now, think about it later" describes my attitude-	.844		
Sometimes, I do buy clothes on the spur of the moment -	.824		
When I go shopping for clothes, I buy things I had not intended to buy-	.747		
If I see clothes that I want, I will buy those-	.634		
Individuals in higher position should take decisions without consulting their subordinates-		.795	
People in senior management should expect subordinates to implement decisions without raising questions-		.722	
Individuals in higher positions should not delegate important tasks to their subordinates-		.713	

	Impulse Purchasing Tendency $\alpha=0.919$	Power-Distance Cultural Construct $\alpha=0.726$	Individualism/Collectivism construct $\alpha=0.675$
Employees are not expected to express disagreement with managers-		.673	
We should encourage group loyalty even if it leads to the impediment of individual goals-			.872
Individuals should sacrifice self-regard for the group-			.742
Individuals should stick with the group through difficulties-			.613
Group well-being is vital relative to individual achievements-			.600

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

The author used multiple linear regression to conduct hypothesis testing (Table-3) by employing p values to ascertain the statistical significance of the independent variables. When p values are less than 0.05, the author can confirm a significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables. With variance inflation factor (VIF) for the variables being less than 2, which is within the acceptable VIF range stated by Pan & Jackson (2008), we can understand there is no issue with multicollinearity.

For Hypothesis 1, there is no statistically significant relationship between gender and impulse purchasing tendency. Although a substantial number of studies claim a significant relationship between gender and impulse purchase behavior (e.g., Nguyen et al., 2003; Tifferet and Herstein, 2012), other studies especially, regarding Gen Y, as in the case with Aruna and Santhi (2015) reveal no significant relationship. The sample is mainly representative of Gen Y and Gen Z, emphasizing the changing pattern in the purchase behavior in these generations.

Regarding H2, the author finds no significant association between age and impulse purchase tendency. This contradicts the findings in Nguyen et al. (2003), and Cakanlar and Nguyen (2019) and can be due to the skewed presence of two generations. Moreover, the sample is missing the more mature clientele of Gen X and Baby Boomers. Furthermore, this finding corroborates the finding from Aruna and Santhi (2015), where they claim socioeconomic profiles do not influence purchase tendency.

H3 examines the association between income levels and impulse purchase tendency. Here, the author finds a significant relationship between income levels and impulse

purchase tendency (p value< 0.05) falling in line with the claim by Bashar et al. (2013) that disposable income is a predictor for impulse purchase tendency.

H4 reveals no significant relationship between individualism/collectivism construct and impulse purchasing behavior. This falls in line with Cakanlar and Nguyen’s (2019) claim in a country like Vietnam; the individualism/ collectivism construct has no relationship to impulse purchasing behavior.

Regarding H5, the author observes no significant association between power-distance culture and impulse purchasing behavior and contradicts a previous study by Cakanlar and Nguyen (2019), which state that for countries such as Vietnam, there is a positive association between power-distance culture and impulse purchasing behavior. An argument for this is that the sample population is representative of Gen Y and Gen Z, whom the author believes have a changing perspective of cultural orientation and are breaking the traditional view of the Bengali society.

Table 3 : Multiple Linear Regression

Model R ² =10.7% Adjusted R ² = 7.10%		Unstandardized		t	Sig.	Hypothesis
		B	Std. Error			
		Coefficients				
1	(Constant)	-.531	.381			
	Gender	.066	.128	.516	.606	Rejected
	Age	-.002	.014	-.014	.887	Rejected
	Household income	.210	.039	5.39	.00	Supported
	Individualism/ Collectivism dimension	-.031	.059	-.529	.598	Rejected
	Power-Distance dimension	-.036	.062	-.594	.566	Rejected

Dependent Variable: Impulse purchasing tendency

The author analyzed whether the impulse purchasing tendency is different across the two generations using a two-sample t-test (Table-4).

H₀: There is a significant difference in impulse purchase tendency between Gen Y and Gen Z.

The author finds a significant difference between the means of impulse purchasing tendency between Gen Y and Gen Z. Generally, Gen Z individuals tend to exhibit a higher impulse purchasing likelihood than Gen Y counterparts.

Table 4 : Two Sample T-test Assuming Unequal Variances

Parameters	Values
t Stat	2.20
t Critical one-tail	1.65
T Critical two-tail	1.98
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.015
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.03

5. DISCUSSION

The study aims to bring in the socio-cultural factors influencing impulse purchasing decisions for a developing nation. Previous studies focused on either the cultural dimensions or the demographic aspects (e.g., Khan et al., 2016). Among the demographic variables, only income impacts the impulse purchase tendency, which falls in line with the findings of Bashar et al. (2013). However, gender and age display no significant influence on impulse purchasing behavior. Our sample, skewed towards two generations (Gen Z and Gen Y), reflects a difference in shopping habits from previous generations. A typical observation with previous generations was that females exhibit more impulsive shopping tendency. However, this reflection does not hold for these generations, even for such a high NFT product as clothing.

Regarding the cultural dimensions, the author learns there is no association between either individualism/collectivism construct or the power distance cultural orientation to impulse purchasing tendency. Typically, studies reveal that western countries with low power-distance indices tend to show a higher impulse purchasing behavior while recent studies involving countries like Vietnam and Turkey reveal a positive relationship between power-distance culture impulse buying behavior (Cakanlar & Nguyen, 2019). Our findings again signify that the younger generations are breaking the norm of accepting a skewed distribution of power in society and do not desire to flaunt power and status, nor do they feel the urge to mimic higher classes. However, the nation is yet to achieve a low power-distance culture, thus reflecting the absence of any relationship between power-distance culture and impulse buying behavior.

A supplementary finding from our analysis is that consumers of Gen Z exhibit substantially more impulse buying tendency than Gen Y consumers. This is an interesting finding for marketers as they aim to target potential market segments.

With companies exploring new markets, especially in developing nations, marketers must comprehend the socio-cultural aspects to adapt their offerings to these markets. Essential findings from this study are that the notion that females exhibit more impulse buying tendency than males may not hold in the Bangladeshi context. Furthermore, the belief that individuals in developing countries show a positive relationship between power-distance culture and impulse buying behavior (Cakanlar & Nguyen,

2019) does not hold while considering the younger generations. However, marketers should stimulate and attract the interests of Gen Z consumers with offers and deals as they exhibit a penchant for impulse purchasing.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Our analysis reveals a low R^2 , meaning the model has a significant unexplained variance. Therefore, it is necessary to incorporate other factors such as situational factors and personality traits to address this variation in impulse buying tendency.

A fundamental observation of the study was the use of non-probability sampling, i.e., convenience sampling of consumers representing two generations and an overrepresentation of males. Overall, it may not be a representative sample. Therefore, future studies should incorporate all demographics. Future studies could include other factors such as situational factors and personality traits and identify different cultural dimensions and scales for analyzing impulse purchasing tendencies, along with analyzing impulse purchasing tendencies of the various generations.

REFERENCES

- Abraham, J., & Dameyasani, A.W. (2013), Impulsive buying, cultural values dimensions, and symbolic meaning of money: a study on college students in Indonesia's capital city and its surrounding, *International Journal of Research Studies in Psychology*, 2 (3), 35-52.
- Abratt, R., & Goodey, S. D., (1990), Unplanned Buying and In-Store Stimuli in Supermarkets, *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 11 (2), 111-21.
- Amos, C., Holmes, G. R., & Keneson, W. C. (2014), A meta- analysis of consumer impulse buying, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 21 (2), 86-97.
- Aruna, S., & Santhi, P. (2015), Impulse Purchase Behaviour Among Generation-Y, *IUP Journal of Marketing Management*, 14 (1), 21-38.
- Bashar, A., Ahmad, I., & Wasiq, M. (2013), A study of influence of demographic factors on consumer impulse buying behavior, *Journal of Management Research*, 13 (3), 145-154.
- Beatty, S.E., & Ferrell, E.M. (1998), Impulse buying: modelling its precursors, *Journal of Retailing*, 74 (2), 169-191.
- Cakanlar, A., & Nguyen, T. (2019), The influence of culture on impulse buying, *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 36, (1), 12-23.
- Chen, H., Ng, S., & Rao, A.R. (2005), Cultural differences in consumer impatience, *Journal of Marketing Research*, 42 (3), 291-301.
- Cobb, C. J., & Hoyer, W. D. (1986), Planned Versus Impulse Purchase Behaviour, *Journal of Retailing*, 62, (4), 384-408.
- Coley, A., & Burgess, B. (2003), Gender differences in cognitive and affective impulse buying, *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 7 (3), 282-295.
- Dhaka Tribune (2020), The Economist: Bangladesh economy relatively safe from Covid-19 fallout, Retrieved from <https://www.dhakatribune.com/bangladesh/2020/05/02/bangladesh-9th-among-emerging-economies-to-deal-with-coronavirus-aftermath>
- Gasiorowska, A. (2011), gender as a moderator of temperamental causes of impulse buying tendency, *Journal of Customer Behavior*, 10 (2), 119-142.
- Hair, J.F. Jr, Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2014), *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM)*, Sage Publications, Los Angeles, CA.
- Hausman, A. (2000), A multi- method investigation of consumer motivations in impulse buying behaviour, *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 17 (5), 403-419.
- Hulten, P., & Vanyushyn, V. (2014), Promotion and shoppers' impulse purchases: the example of clothes, *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 31, (2), 94-102.

- Hofstede, G.H., & Hofstede, G. (2001), *Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviours, Institutions and Organizations across Nations*, Sage, Riverside, CA.
- Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G.J., & Minkov, M. (1991), *Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind*, 2, McGraw Hill, London.
- Hofstede-Insights. (n.d.), WHAT ABOUT BANGLADESH? , Retrieved from <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country/bangladesh/>
- Kacen, J. J., & Lee, J.A. (2002), The influence of culture on consumer impulsive buying behaviour, *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 12(2), 163-176.
- Kacen, J.J., & Lee, J.A. (2008), Cultural influences on consumer satisfaction with impulse and planned purchase decisions, *Journal of Business Research*, 61 (3), 265-272.
- Kagitcibasi, C. (1997), Individualism and collectivism, *Handbook of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 3, 1-49.
- Kenhove, P.V., Janssens, W. and Wijen, K. (2008), *Marketing Research with SPSS*, Pearson Education, UK.
- Khan, N., Hui, L.H., Chen, T.B., & Hong Yong Hoe H. Y. (2016), Impulse Buying Behaviour of Generation Y in Fashion Retail, *International Journal of Business and Management*, 11(1), 144-151.
- Kollat, D. T., & P. Willett, R. P. (1967), Customer Impulse Purchasing Behaviour, *Journal of Marketing Research*, 4 (February), 21-31.
- Kongakaradecha, S., & Khemarangsang, A. (2012), A pilot study of impulse buying behaviour in Bangkok, Thailand, Proceedings of the 2nd National and International Graduate Study Conference.
- Lee, J.A., & Richard, B. (1998), Dimensions of Individualism and Collectivism at the Individual Level of Analysis, working paper, University of Hawaii, Manoa.
- Mattila, A.S., & Wirtz, J. (2008), The role of store environmental stimulation and social factors on impulse purchasing, *Journal of Services Marketing*, 22(7), 562-567.
- Minur, Z, Muehlstein O., & Nauhbar (2015), Bangladesh: The Surging Consumer Market Nobody Saw Coming, The Boston Consulting Group, Retrieved from <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2015/bangladesh-the-surging-consumer-market-nobody-saw-coming.aspx>
- Nguyen, T. T. M., Kwon, J., Garold, L., & Sandra, G. L. (2003), An Exploratory Investigation into Impulse Buying Behavior in a Transitional Economy: A Study of Urban Consumers in Vietnam, *Journal of International Marketing*, 11, (2), 13-35.
- Oyserman, Daphna (2006), High Power, Low Power, and Equality: Culture Beyond Individualism and Collectivism, *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 16, (4), 352-56.

Pan, Y., & Jackson, R. T. (2008). Ethnic difference in the relationship between acute inflammation and serum ferritin in US adult males', *Epidemiology and Infection*, 136, 421-431.

Peck, J., & Childers, T.L. (2006), If I touch it I have to have it: individual and environmental influences on impulse purchases, *Journal of Business Research*, 59 (6), 765-769.

Rawlings, D., Boldero, J., & Wiseman, F. (1995), The Interaction of Age with Impulsiveness and Venturesomeness in the Prediction of Adolescent Sexual Behaviour, *Personality and Individual Differences*, 19(1), 117-20.

Rook, D.W. (1987), "The buying impulse", *Journal of Consumer Research*, 14, 189-99.

Rook, D.W., & Fisher, R.J. (1995), "Trait and normative aspects of impulsive buying behaviour", *Journal of Consumer Research*, 22 (3), 305-13.

Tifferet, S., & Herstein, R. (2012), Gender differences in brand commitment, impulse buying, and hedonic consumption, *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 21 (3), 176-182.

Triandis, H. C., Bontempo, R., Villareal, M. J., & Lucca, N. (1988), Individualism and Collectivism: Cross-Cultural Perspectives on Self-In group Relations, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 54 (2), 323-38.

WJSchroer, (n.d.), Generations X, Y, Z and the Others, Retrieved from <http://socialmarketing.org/archives/generations-xy-z-and-the-others/>

Yang, D. J., Huang, K. C., & Feng, X. (2011), A Study of the Factors that Affect the Impulsive Cosmetics Buying of Female Consumers in Kaohsiung, *International Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 2 (24), 275-28

Zhang, Y., Winterich, K. P., & Mittal, V. (2010), Power distance belief and impulsive buying, *Journal of Marketing Research*, 47 (5), 945-954.